

ISic2962

I.Sicily inscription 2962

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

urn

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Fusco, scavo governativo FF.SS. 1882

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 234

Physical Description

A circular marble urn with an eagle on the lid. Inscribed panel on the front of the urn surrounded by garland held by a pair of naked cupids

Dimensions

Height 31 cm

Width 28 cm

Depth 28 cm

Layout

Latin text on three lines, in a rectangular panel with moulded surround

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Ornate but slightly irregular letters of the high imperial style. B has smaller upper eye; R and Q have long tails; E tends towards the later narrower form and shows some variety; interpunct in the style of an elongated comma after every word

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Q(uintus) · Cornifici(us) ·
2. Q(uinti) · lib(ertus) · Hermes ·
3. pie · salve ·

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Quintus Cornificius Hermes, freedman of Quintus, a dutiful man, farewell!

Commentary

CIL states that the urn is in Palermo museum, but this appears to have been an error.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492321

EDCS 23400459

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.8314 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 85

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014